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IMAGE

Integrated Methods for Advanced Geothermal Exploration

IMAGE-D4.02: Summary Report of WP 4.02: Active Seismic with VSP

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Introduction & summary

This report contains compiled results and synthesis for Task 4.2 within Work Package (WP) 4 of the EU funded IMAGE project. Within Task 4.2 several different Vertical Seismic Profiling (VSP) experiments including zero-offset VSP, far-offset VSP, multi-offset VSP, as well as source comparison and passive seismic monitoring were carried out in two boreholes within the Krafla high temperature geothermal field, NE-Iceland. Additional to the VSP experiments, new sonic log, televiwer and borehole cuttings analyses were carried out in one of the two boreholes to improve the geological interpretation of the VSP data. The surveys were successfully completed and good data were obtained and processed for both wells. Integration of the results from the VSP experiments with the borehole analysis enabled successful linkage of the key lithological boundaries within the wells proving the ability of VSP to image key boundaries in a heterogeneous basalt dominated subsurface sequence. Utilizing the VSP results to look-ahead of the penetrated interval also revealed important reflectivity results below the well. This provides important verification of the technique. However, constraining the nature of the reflectivity in terms of fluid types, structure or magma remains a challenge. In summary, Task 4.2 has produced a very large amount of high quality data and demonstrated the ability of the technique to image the complex subsurface of geothermally prospective volcanic edifices. The volume and quality of data has also created a highly valuable resource, which will enable numerous future investigations to look into the seismic structure of volcanic geothermal fields.

VSP field operations in borehole K-18, Krafla, NE-Iceland (June, 2014).

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1 Introduction

The EU funded IMAGE project (Integrated Methods for Advanced Geothermal Exploration) was meant to address the problems encountered in geothermal exploration and reservoir assessment through a three-step approach:

1. Understanding of underlying processes, operating at European to local scales, controlling the spatial distribution of critical exploration parameters. With focus on detecting and interpreting features that can be determined remotely through application of advanced or innovative exploration technologies.
2. Improving well-established exploration techniques for imaging and detection beyond the current state of the art and testing of new geological, geophysical and geochemical methods that can provide reliable information on critical subsurface exploration parameters.
3. Integrating all existing and new data derived from new exploration techniques to provide predictive models for site characterization and well siting.

This three-step structure is adapted to specific geological environments with the basic subdivision into magmatic systems, subproject SP2 and basement/sedimentary systems, subproject SP3 (Figure 1). An important aspect of the IMAGE project was also to provide opportunities for young scientists to participate in international geothermal research projects.

Figure 1. Concept of the IMAGE project, workplan and structure.

The key objectives of work package **WP4** is to develop and test geophysical exploration methods for magmatic environments to detect, prior to drilling, zones of high permeability, steam and magma, and to estimate reservoir temperature (Figure 2). Special focus is on the detection of supercritical fluids in geothermal systems and to assess the possible potential of such systems. WP4 is set up as six different tasks including:

- Task 4.1:** Passive seismic at magmatic
- Task 4.2:** Active seismic with Vertical Seismic Profiling (VSP)
- Task 4.3:** High temperature (>380°C) measurement
- Task 4.4:** Estimating crustal stress and fracture permeability
- Task 4.5:** Tracer for supercritical conditions
- Task 4.6:** Imaging deep structure with electrical resistivity

This report deals specifically with the activities associated with Task 4.2 and incorporates results of the VSP experiment carried out at the Krafla high-temperature geothermal field.

1.1 Project aims and activities

The main objective of Task 4.2 was to assess the applicability of VSP surveying as a method for sub-surface mapping in volcanic geothermal fields including zones of magma, supercritical fluid, superheated steam and high permeability. The Krafla geothermal field in NE-Iceland was especially chosen as a test site since its subsurface structure is quite well known due to the wealth of information available from different studies and data from the many wells that have been drilled there, but also because of the recent drilling into magma (Friðleifsson et al., 2014). Previously applied geophysical studies including resistivity surveys and micro-earthquakes studies from a passive seismic network, provide a basis to compare results of surface exploration to joint interpretation of borehole seismic imaging and borehole geology and geophysical logs. Knowledge about the sub-surface geology of the Krafla geothermal area is largely known from various borehole data and drilling investigations, which can be compared with the results of the borehole seismic imaging. The VSP experiment has been tested as a method for imaging a range of features important for magmatic geothermal exploration including:

1. Layered igneous stratigraphy including basalt flows, hyaloclastites, sills, intrusions and volcanoclastic sediments
2. Dipping features such as dikes and sills
3. Porosity, fractures, and faults (important for fluid flow and reservoirs)
4. Magma (in sills, dikes or magma chambers)
5. Fluid saturation, supercritical fluids and steam/gas caps

The VSP survey was carried out successfully in two boreholes in Krafla, K-18 and K-26, in May and June 2014 by ÍSOR, GFZ and VBPR with the support of Landsvirkjun. The *Field Report* (Appendix A.1) includes a summary of field operations as well as acquisition and description of field data. The survey encompassed several different experiments within the two wells, which included zero-offset VSP, far-offset VSP, multi-offset VSP, source comparison and passive seismic monitoring. In addition to the VSP experiments, sonic and televiwer logs were run in well K-18 and borehole cuttings re-analyzed in that well to correlate the geological structure to the VSP data.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of a central volcano with a geothermal field located within its associated caldera (ÍSOR).

2 Geological setting

The Krafla high temperature geothermal area is situated in the northern rift zone of Iceland, an onshore extension of the Kolbeinsey Ridge (Figure 3). The Kolbeinsey Ridge in turn represents the spreading axis between the NW European and East Greenland conjugate rifted continental margins. The Krafla area is dominated by an active central volcano with an associated caldera, located in a NS oriented fissure system. The Krafla volcano is about 300,000 years old. Its volcanic activity is episodic, occurring at 250–1000 year intervals, and based on the last volcanic episode, each episode apparently lasts 10–20 years. This last episode, known as the “Krafla Fires”, lasted from 1975 to 1984, resulted in 21 tectonic events and 9 volcanic eruptions (Björnsson, 1985; Einarsson, 1991) (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Simplified geological map of Iceland. Abbreviations: ERZ, Eastern rift zone; NRZ, Northern rift zone; RLRZ, Reykjanes–Langjökull rift zone (ÍSOR).

The Krafla geothermal field is located in an 8 – 10 km wide caldera within the Krafla central volcano (Figure 4). The caldera is largely filled with basaltic lavas and hyaloclastites. Rhyolites have erupted periodically in minor volumes forming subglacial rhyolitic ridges that are mainly found at or outside the margins of the caldera (Figure 4). A magma body beneath the caldera is estimated to be at a depth of 3 to 7 km, based on S-wave attenuation during the most recent eruptive episodes (Einarsson, 1978). More recently, this was supported by refraction and passive seismic methods (e.g. Brandsdóttir et al., 1997; Staples et al., 1997; Tang et al., 2008). Recent magnetotelluric (MT) and micro-seismic studies further indicated the presence of magma chamber, which is divided into a western and an eastern part (Friðleifsson et al., 2014). Its outline is roughly determined by a low resistivity zone assuming the top of the chamber at 2.5–3 km depth.

In the Krafla geothermal field, a 60 MWe geothermal electrical power plant is operated by Landsvirkjun, the national power company of Iceland. In total, 44 deep wells have been drilled in the area to explore and produce high-temperature steam and fluids (see Figure 5). All the wells are located within the Krafla caldera where temperatures can reach 340°C at depths as shallow as 2 km. At the Krafla power plant, high- and low pressure steam from 18 boreholes drives two 30 MWe turbines. The first IDDP (Iceland Deep Drilling Project) well was drilled in Krafla in 2009. The objective was to drill a vertical well down to a depth of 4500 m into the roots of a conventional high temperature hydrothermal system to produce water at supercritical conditions and bring it to the surface as 400-600°C superheated steam. When the borehole reached 2100 m, it penetrated into magma and drilling was stopped. The steam generated by the borehole reached a temperature of 430-450°C. Therefore it is one of the hottest boreholes in the world. It is estimated that the potential energy production of the borehole could be between 25-40 MWe.

The lithology in the central part of the Krafla caldera roughly consists of extrusive igneous rocks (hyaloclastite and lava piles), which dominate down to approximately 400–1000 m (b.s.l.) whereas basaltic intrusions dominate below that (Figure 6). The elevation of the area is about 500 m. As seen on the profile in Figure 6, beneath Suðurhlíðar, there is a prominent 200–400 m thick felsic intrusion. Felsic intrusions are not as prominent west of Hveragil and in the easternmost part of Suðurhlíðar (K-18). Thin, felsic or intermediate intrusions, however, occur at variable depths in Leirbotnar and Vítismór. Furthermore, it has been established that there is felsic magma at shallow depths in the crust since felsic magma has been reached twice by drilling, on the one hand in Suðurhlíðar (below 2500 m MD in well K-39) and on the other hand in Vítismór (at a little less than 2100 m MD (measured depth) in well IDDP-1). There is also up to 200–300 m thick pile of felsic intrusions at around 900–1400 m (b.s.l.) beneath Suðurhlíðar (Figure 6). Gabbroic intrusions follow at around 1300–1900 m (b.s.l.) in the wells in that area which is evident in the lithology profile of each well (K-18, K-19, and K-39). Felsic intrusions are not as prominent west of Hveragil and in the easternmost part of Suðurhlíðar (well K-18).

Legend

Postglacial lavas

- Historical lava, younger than 870 AD
- Prehistoric lava < 2900 years old
- Lava 2900-4500 years old
- Lava 4500-6100 years old
- Lava > 6100 years old, a. Basalt, b. Andesite

Bedrock

- Subglacial hyaloclastite, Weischelian, a. Younger, b. Older
- Hyaloclastite, a. Early Bruhnes, b. Older than Bruhnes
- a. Lava cap on hyaloclastite, b. Interglacial shield
- Interglacial lava, a. Late Quaternary, b. Early Quaternary
- a. Andesite, b. Dacite
- Rhyolite

Superficial deposits

- a. Undefined surface deposits, b. Rock slide

- a. Tephra, b. Tephra Crater

Symbols

- a. Scoria or spatter cone, b. Crater row
- a. Pleistocene crater, b. Postglacial shield crater
- Hydrothermal volcanic explosion crater
- a. Lava tube, b. Lava channel
- Collapse pit
- Caldera rim
- a. Lava margin, b. Inferred lava margin
- a. Fault, b. Open fissure
- Geothermal surface manifestation
- Inferred magma chamber
- Wells (K-18 and K-26)

Figure 4. Geological map of the Krafla caldera displaying the location of the Petrel model cross section shown in Figure 6 (modified after Sæmundsson et al. 2012).

Figure 5. Location of wells and the stratigraphic cross section within Krafla geothermal field as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Simplified stratigraphic cross section from W to E through Leirhnjúkur, Vítismór, Leirbotnar and Suðurhlíðar (modified after Mortensen et al. 2009).

3 VSP operation and data

3.1 Magmatic geothermal exploration and VSP

Task 4.2 of the IMAGE project was designed to test the applicability of the VSP method for subsurface mapping in volcanic geothermal fields including zones of magmatic bodies, fractures and dykes, zones of supercritical fluids, superheated steam and high permeability. VSP experiments have previously been successfully used to image sub-surface stratigraphy within layered volcanic sequences from the North Atlantic Igneous Province (e.g. in Iceland: Planke and Flóvenz, 1996, and the Faroe Islands: Christie et al., 2006). However, the IMAGE project provides the first assessment of the method as a geothermal exploration technique in a high temperature area in Iceland. In geothermal exploration in general, VSP still plays a minor part. However, there are some examples of VSP being used in the context of geothermal exploration in other areas, for example Nakagome et al. (1998), Riedel et al. (2015), and Hlousek et al. (2015).

Vertical Seismic Profiling (VSP) is a geophysical method combining seismic sources at the surface (or near-surface) with receivers (e.g. geophones) placed inside a borehole (Figure 7). Distinction is made between different VSP geometries, depending on the distribution or location of the sources at the surface. There are zero-offset VSPs, where the source is as close as possible to the well-head, offset VSPs where the source is at a greater distance to the wellhead, and the more extensive approaches like multi-offset, multi-azimuth and complete 3D surveys.

Figure 7. Principle of a Vertical Seismic Profiling (VSP) experiment with receivers placed in a borehole and one source located at the earth's surface. Modified after Hardage (2000).

Figure 8. Schematic drawing of ray paths and event pattern for a zero-offset VSP. a) Depth model of two horizontal reflectors (solid bold lines). Colored lines show ray paths of a wave emitted by a source (S). b) Associated travel time section as it is recorded by the receivers in the borehole. Letters A–D mark four specific receivers and associated recorded events: A – First downgoing arrival (first break, FB), A_1 , primary reflection (A_2) and downgoing multiple (A_3); B – Primary upgoing arrival (primary reflection); C – Primary downgoing arrival after being refracted at the interface; D – Mode-converted downgoing arrival. Modified after Yilmaz (1990).

The most common and likewise simplest geometry is the zero-offset survey. Here, the interpretations are straightforward and it can be used to confidently tie geology and drill logs with the VSP and surface seismic, as well as multiple reflections can easily be identified (Hinds and Kuzmiski, 2002). A fundamental property of a VSP is that the recorded wave field can be distinguished into upgoing and downgoing components as shown in Figure 8. Furthermore, it can be used to determine information of seismic velocities, deconvolution parameters, primary and multiple reflections and other subsurface properties affecting the wave field in the proximity of the well (e.g. Kennett et al., 1980). Hence, modern VSP surveys can combine the whole range of seismic wave analyses to provide a high resolution image of the subsurface. For additional explanations regarding the VSP method, the reader is referred to the comprehensive work of Hardage (2000).

An important aspect of planning and analyzing VSP experiments is the pre-assessment or forward modelling of potential targets such as dykes or fracture zones and reservoirs. Synthetic seismic forward modelling, therefore, provides a valuable potential for attempting to couple observed with predicted results. Synthetic modelling was performed as a part of the VSP experiment reported by Planke and Flóvenz (1996) from the YT-2 borehole at Laugaland, N-Iceland, some 60 km WSW of Krafla. In the YT-2 borehole, multiple dykes intrude a lava-dominated Tertiary sequence. Finite-difference synthetic seismograms were modelled based on a velocity model with and without observed dykes (Figure 9). Interpreted first arrival picks for the two experiments are displayed in a reduced travel time plot in Figure 9c.

Observations from the modelling included (Figure 9):

1. The first arrival wavelet (orange arrow) is longer on the dyke model data than on the lava flow model.
2. Upgoing energy (reflections; red arrows) are clearly identified in the lava flow model. In contrast, no upgoing events are identified in the dyke model data. Blue arrows show upgoing events that are likely numerical artifacts.
3. The layered lava flow model have a more ringing character than the more heterogeneous dyke model.

Figure 9. Finite-difference synthetic seismogram models of YT-2 in Laugaland, 60 km WSW of Krafla. A. Velocity model without dykes. B. Velocity model with dykes. C. Reduced travel time plot of first arrivals. The modelling shows that sub-vertical dykes can have a significant effect on VSP wave propagation by increasing the interval velocity with about 10% in the deeper part of the well, below ca 500 m (Planke and Flóvenz, 1996).

The objective of Task 4.2 was to investigate known problems associated with surface seismic reflection techniques, which suffer from high scattering of seismic wave energy in volcanic sequences (Planke et al., 2000; Nelson et al., 2009). Part of the problem with imaging volcanic rocks comes from the very wide ranges of velocities (much wider than is normally present in sedimentary rocks) that are very regularly present and intimately distributed and mixed within different volcanic facies (e.g. Figure 10). This heterogeneity is clearly demonstrated in Figure 11, which displays a summary of the seismic properties of ODP Hole 642 in the Vøring Basin, offshore Norwegian. The wide range of variables that affect the velocity structure of volcanic and magmatic subsurface features are additionally complicated in active volcanic regions and may include:

- Original magma composition (mafic versus felsic e.g. Pechinig et al., 2005; Bartetzko et al., 2005).
- State of magma (molten or partially molten, Singh et al., 1998).
- Phenocryst abundance and crystal size (e.g. Christensen and Salisbury, 1975; Watton et al., 2013).
- Porosity and fractures (vesicles, cooling fractures, faults e.g. Wilkins et al., 1991).
- Fragmentation, erosion and redeposition (primary, secondary; tuffs, hyaloclastites, volcanogenic sediments, e.g. Schmincke et al., 1995; Watton et al., 2014).
- Alteration to secondary minerals such as smectite and chlorite e.g. Planke et al., 1999a; Walton and Schiffman, 2003).
- Volcanic facies e.g. lavas, hyaloclastite, intrusions (Planke et al. 1999b; Nelson et al. 2009; Millett et al., 2014).
- Filling of voids and fractures (zeolites, silicates e.g. Lebedev and Kern, 1999).
- Fluid fill (water versus gas versus air e.g. Christensen and Salisbury, 1975).

Figure 10. Velocity and density ranges for different volcanic facies compiled from the SIMBA project database (after Nelson et al., 2009).

Figure 11. Summary of seismic properties in ODP Hole 642E (after Planke, 1994). Note the large variations in sonic velocities within individual basalt flows. Individual flow units are much thinner than the resolution of conventional seismic reflection data. Seismic reflections are therefore interference phenomena from the high-impedance contrasts within the lava pile.

In order to constrain the complex interaction of these variables within the subsurface of the Krafla field study area, an integrated study of the K-18 borehole was done to incorporate existing data with new data collected and interpreted as a part of the IMAGE project. This analysis included wireline log analysis specifically focusing on televiwer analysis (e.g. Blischke et al., 2007) and wireline sonic velocity analyses (e.g. Nelson et al., 2009) along with an appraisal and application of alternative cuttings analysis methods (e.g. Millett et al., 2014) to magmatic geothermal wells. The results of these borehole analysis reports are presented in Appendices A.4, A.5, A.6 and A.7. This integration has enabled confident comparison of the VSP study data to the geophysical and geological model for intervals penetrated by the two VSP experiment wells at Krafla. This constraint is important for the assessment of the VSP results in context of the objective of Task 4.2.

3.2 Operations summary and data

The Krafla VSP experiment is summarized in Table 1 and encompasses two zero-offset VSP, two far-offset VSP and a limited multi-source-offset VSP (MSP). A detailed field report outlining all details of the VSP operations and acquisition is in Appendix A.1. The measurements were carried out in two receiver wells, K-18 and K-26, approximately 1900 m apart (Figure 12). For well K-18 the source offset was about 29 m for the zero-offset VSP and 1903 m for the far-offset VSP. For well K-26 the zero-offset was about 36 m and the far-offset 1572 m from the well. The water-filled pits INGI and JON were used as zero-offset sources for K-18 and K-26, respectively, and the water filled pit THORSTEIN as far-offset source for both wells. The locations of the water-filled pits are shown in Figure 13, as well as the locations of other seismic sources in the VSP survey. For the zero-offset VSP, an air gun source was deployed into the artificial water pits, JON and INGI, near the wellheads.

Table 1. VSP experiment carried out in the Krafla geothermal field.

No.	Experiment	Priority	Well
1	Zero-Offset VSP (ZOVSP)	High	K-18, K-26
2	Far-Offset VSP (FOVSP)	Medium	K-18, K-26
3	Multi-Offset VSP (MSP)	Medium	K-18, K-26
4	Source Comparisons	Low	K-18, K-26
5	Passive Seismic Monitoring	Low	K-18

The far-offset source, THORSTEIN, was used for orientation purposes. Several shot holes, THOR 1-12, were aligned along a nearly 3 km N-S lying and 2 km E-W lying profiles for the multi-offset VSP (MSP), which was of lower priority than the zero-offset VSP. Figure 12 shows the locations of the shot holes. The shot holes were drilled with a 6" steel casing down to 9 m. The water filled pits JON, INGI, KARL and THORSTEIN were dug with an excavator. The JON and INGI pits, used for the zero offset shots, were coated with plastic material to keep the water from leaking out and sand from interfering with the air guns.

Both well K-18 and K-26 are nearly vertical and their measured depths are 2215 m and 2127 m, respectively. Well K-26 is used as an injection well whereas well K-18 is non-productive and used as a monitoring well. The inner diameter of well K-18 is 13 $\frac{3}{8}$ " (245 mm) in the cased section and 8 $\frac{1}{2}$ " in the open hole section starting from 663 m depth. Well K-26 has no open hole section, the inner diameters of the well is 9 $\frac{5}{8}$ " in the casing section and 7" in the liner section. Borehole summaries, including figures of the well casing depths and diameters are available in the field report in Appendix A.1.

An array of eight three-component geophones was installed on the surface between each well and the zero-offset source to record the source spectra and to check for influences of surface waves in the wells. Relative locations of the geophones with respect to the well and zero-offset are shown in Figure 13.

All data produced for the Krafla VSP experiments have been compiled and organized into a spreadsheet-based database that is linked to the field report Appendix A.1. The data files are all available in the following digital folder structures:

- Data D.1 Field data (ZOVSP, MSP, Geophone, Reftec, Seismometer, Navigation)
- Data D.2 Processed data (ZOVSP, NMO, corridor stack for P and S waves; velocity-depth curves/velocity models)

Figure 12. Location map of the VSP measurements in the Krafla geothermal field showing locations of shot points. Shot holes THOR1 to THOR12 (red markers) show the multi-offset shot locations. Water filled pits used for air gun shots and far-offset shots, are shown in blue and location of source test shots in yellow.

Figure 13. Location map of the VSP measurements in the Krafla geothermal field showing locations of surface receiver positions. K-18 and K-26 (green markers) show the receiver wells. Locations of seismic stations are shown with orange, red and blue diamond markers.

4 Additional data and methods

As part of the IMAGE project Task 4.2, a range of existing data, collected during the development of the Krafla high temperature geothermal field, were made available. These data formed the basis of the decision to use Krafla as the high temperature magmatic field case study for Task 4.2. Additional data, acquired during the Task 4.2 activities, were collected to enable the project goals to be realized. Within this section a summary of all the data sources utilized or made available to the IMAGE project are given.

4.1 Borehole data

4.1.1 K-18 borehole

Table 2. Summary of borehole data sets for well K-18 utilized within the TASK 4.2 IMAGE project activities. Abbreviate: OS (Orkustofnun / National Energy Authority) and LV (Landsvirkjun / National Power Company of Iceland).

Well	Data type or resource	Description	Source / affiliation
K-18	Wireline	Caliper (CAL)	OS (1981) & ÍSOR/LV (2014)
K-18	Wireline	Gamma ray (GR API)	OS (1981) & ÍSOR/LV (2014)
K-18	Wireline	Resistivity 64 (RES 64)	OS (1981) & ÍSOR/LV (2014)
K-18	Wireline	Resistivity 16 (RES 16)	OS (1981) & ÍSOR/LV (2014)
K-18	Wireline	Neutron (NN)	OS (1981) & ÍSOR/LV (2014)
K-18	Wireline	Televiwer (ABI43 log)	ÍSOR/LV (2014)
K-18	Wireline	Sonic log (DTC)	ÍSOR/LV (2014)
K-18	Wireline	Temperature log	OS (1981) & ÍSOR/LV (2014)
K-18	Lithology log	Cuttings analysis	OS (1981)
K-18	Lithology log	Cuttings analysis	VBPR (2015)
K-18	Report	Initial geology report	OS (1981)

4.1.2 K-26 borehole

Table 3. Summary of borehole data sets for well K-26 utilized within Task 4.2 activities.

Well	Data type or resource	Description	Source / affiliation
K-26	Wireline	Caliper (CAL)	OS (1991)
K-26	Wireline	Gamma ray (GR API)	OS (1991)
K-26	Wireline	Resistivity 64 (RES 64)	OS (1991)
K-26	Wireline	Resistivity 16 (RES 16)	OS (1991)
K-26	Wireline	Neutron (NN)	OS (1991)
K-26	Wireline	Temperature log	OS (1991) & ÍSOR/LV (2014)
K-26	Lithology log	Cuttings analysis	OS (1991)
K-26	Report	Initial geology report	OS (1991)

4.1.3 Additional data / reports

A number of reports connected or relevant to Task 4.2 were published during the completion of the task. All these new reports are available in the appendices of this report. Additional data and resources available within the project included the following:

ÍSOR petrel model:

All wireline log data, lithological data and geological boundaries etc. for the Krafla geothermal field have been incorporated into a Petrel hosted geological model. Within the model, all major surfaces and mapped structural elements are integrated.

MT, gravity and micro-earthquake data:

Árnason et al. (2008) reported on the results of a gravity, micro-earthquake and MT study which provided inference as to the possible location of the magma chamber beneath Krafla.

ÍSOR 48-channel geophone array:

- Instrument: Geometrics StrataVÍSOR NZ, 24 channels, with Geode extension for extra 24 ch.
- Geophone interval: 10 m; length of line: 470 m; sample interval: 0.001; format: seg2.
- Recording time: 4 s before 5th of June, then 5 s (777 / 965 kb).
- Line was deployed in two locations: west of K-18 and east of K-26.
- The seg2-data files were matched to shot times by using file creation time and confirmed as data by visual inspection in a seismic viewer program.

4.2 Microseismicity methods

The most important source of data is the VSP tools string (type Sercel SlimWaveTM), that was lowered within K-18 and passively recorded microseismic data during periods when no active VSP survey was ongoing; hence recording is mainly limited to night times. However, the geophones on the VSP string cannot withstand high temperatures for a long time. Therefore, the geophones had to be pulled out at times for cooling and/or the well had to be periodically flushed with water for cooling purposes; introducing strong noise. This made some of the passive seismic data unusable for the purpose of detecting microseismic events. In addition to the string of downhole geophones, some permanent and temporary seismometers were deployed in the surrounding area. Data from these stations were integrated with the downhole recorded VSP data for short time intervals when microseismic events were identified on the VSP sensors.

Landsvirkjun operates a network of permanent seismic stations. The station locations are shown in Figure 13. During the VSP survey, IMAGE operated three seismic stations (VIT, HVG and THP; Figure 13). The DRG-project (DRG – Deep Roots of Geothermal Systems supported by the GEORG – Geothermal Research Group) operated a dense network of seismic stations during the VSP survey (Figure 13).

4.3 Wireline logging methods

When high temperature wells are drilled in Iceland, neutron (NN), gamma ray, resistivity and caliper logging is generally conducted at the end of each drilling stage to obtain information about the lithology and width/volume of the well. An exception was made at the end of the first drilling stage of K-26, as only caliper was logged. The reason for this was that logging of resistivity, NN and gamma in wells with larger diameter than 311 mm (12¼") had proven to give limited information about the lithology (Guðmundsson et al., 1991a). These logging runs were done in well K-18 ten years earlier, in addition to a SP log, and it appeared that the quality of the NN log was poor and

the gamma log was inapplicable, although the resistivity logs were acceptable (Friðleifsson and Stefánsson, 1981). An overview of the logs in K-18 and K-26 is presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Televiwer and sonic logging was performed in well K-18 in the Krafla field in October 2014 as a part of the IMAGE project (Appendices A.5, A.6 and A7). Results of structural analysis of the televiwer data indicate that joints and fractures within the logged interval predominantly strike NW-SE to N-S and dip towards NE/E. Fractures and joints observed in the televiwer images are interpreted to be filled/cemented or tight/discontinuous, and in several cases partially open. No major open fractures were observed in the logged interval. Interfaces observed in the televiwer images are considered to mark intrusion boundaries, and can be roughly divided into steeply dipping N-S and NE-SW striking interfaces (dykes) and sub-horizontal ~WNW-ESE striking, ~SSW-dipping interfaces (sill intrusions). The latter are in some cases non-planar, which may suggest that magma intruded an unconsolidated intrusive material. The quality of the sonic data is generally very good. But, because of well casing down to 663 m, no sonic data is available for the upper part of the well.

4.4 Borehole cuttings analysis methods

Borehole cuttings analysis of K-18 was done in late 2014 (Appendix A.4). Access to washed and dried cuttings boxes collected at 2 m intervals, along with cuttings cards were available (at least one or the other but commonly both) for the entire well. Cuttings analysis was carried out during drilling of the well in 1981. The purpose of re-analyzing the cuttings was to apply some of the recent developments in volcanic cuttings analysis (e.g. Millett et al., 2014), developed from offshore wells, to well K-18 in order to assess the applicability of the method to geothermal wells and to compare the results with previous work. A focus of the new cuttings analysis was to attempt to identify the volcanic facies encountered in the well. The wide range of diagnostic alteration minerals which are used to identify the sub-surface thermal conditions of geothermal fields was not investigated in this study, and for these, the original ÍSOR report is utilized throughout. The classification scheme utilized for this project was modified after the approach of Millett et al. (2014) and is discussed in details in Appendix A.4.

5 VSP processing

Quality control (QC) and seismic processing of the acquired VSP data were carried out by DECO Geophysical SC. In the *Processing Report* (Appendix A.2) the processing steps are described in detail for each zero-offset VSP in both wells (K-18 and K-26). As part of a Master's Thesis, further processing and imaging techniques were tested (Appendix A.8).

5.1 QC Processing

A data and field QC were carried out. These comprise the documentation of the operations as well as preliminary seismic QC including signal-to-noise ratio tests and frequency analyses of the acquired data. Results are documented in Appendix A.1.

For the seismic QC the following key objectives were itemized:

- Check data integrity for e.g. corrupted data files
- Verify header consistency
- Scrutinize field data visually
- Determine quality attributes like frequency content, noise channels, and signal-to-noise ratios (SNR)
- Compare different applied sources

Thereby, it comprises header inspections (header QC), frequency behaviour/content (cf. Section Source Comparison), and attribute analyses like SNR and noise.

The results of the QC of each individual experiment are summarized in Table 4. The signal-to-noise ratios were determined by $A1 / A0 = \text{SNR}$. Here, A1 is the RMS (root-mean-squared) amplitude of the signal 100 ms after the first-break and A0 the RMS amplitude of the noise measured 100 ms before the first-break.

Table 4. Summary of the QC of the VSP experiments.

Experiment	Source	Overall Data Quality	Headers	SNR	Useful Signal Frequencies	Remarks
K-18 Zero-Offset VSP	Air gun	good	27% no GPS, otherwise OK	3-150 (deepest to shallow levels)	10-40 Hz (16 Hz peak)	Only clamped receiver levels can be used for processing;
						A1 Amplitudes decays with decreasing pressure
K-18 Far-Offset / Check-Shot	Dynamite	good	OK	27.mar	5-70 Hz	Only clamped receiver levels can be used for processing
	(pond)				(<130 Hz)	
K-26 Zero-Offset	Air gun	good	FFID do not increase with depths	05.okt	10-40 Hz	Only clamped receivers with good signal quality
K-18 MSP	Dynamite (shot hole)	moderate	OK	good	10-40 Hz	No clear seismic picture detectable
K-26 MSP	Dynamite (shot hole)	bad	OK	-	-	Only 57 shot records; No FB detectable

5.2 ZO VSP processing | K-18

5.2.1 Processing flow

Figure 14 shows the processing flow as applied for the zero-offset VSP. In general, the presented processing flow represents the standard processing procedure as widely applied in the industry (e.g. Hinds et al., 1996).

The raw single data files are loaded together with the associated geometry information. Traces are then depth sorted, edited and stacked for same recording depths. The result of this often called pre-processing raw shot gather is used for further processing procedure which are separated in a P-wave and S-wave processing scheme. Previously, the data were reoriented from its local coordinate system recorded at each receiver to the ray-based coordinate system. Both parts include amplitude corrections (e.g. removing spherical spreading effects and attenuation), deconvolution, bandpass filtering and wavefield separation. From the first arrival times (first-breaks) and the depth of the receivers, a 1D velocity profile is determined for both P- and S-wave first arrivals. With help of the picked travel times further velocity analyses can be carried out incorporating reduced travel time (RTT) curves as well as averaged interval velocities. Finally, the normal-moveout (NMO) corrected wave fields are used to determine the corridor stack for the zero-offset VSP for both P- and S-waves.

The NMO correction is carried out to align the upgoing wave field to its two-way travel time (TWT).

In this reduced upgoing wave field reflections coming from the near borehole surroundings appear horizontally aligned and can be linked directly with the depths from which they emanate.

The corridor stack is a common result of the zero-offset VSP processing. Therefore, some of the traces (i.e. a selected corridor) of a NMO processed section (i.e. the reduced upgoing wave field) are summed (*stacked*) to retain only the primary reflections. The summation is applied over a time window, usually 200-300 ms, after the first breaks (Sheriff, 2002) in order to exclude most of the multiples and likewise emphasize the primary events along the well path. This is often called *outer corridor stack*. In contrast, when data are stacked excluding this corridor, one speaks of an *inner corridor stack*. The latter is often used to study multiples.

Table 5. K-18 zero-offset VSP summary.

No. of geophones	17 levels (lowermost 6 clamped)
Intertool spacing	10 m
Reference point	10 m above first geophone
No. overlapped positions	1
Receiver station interval	2.5 m
Real measured depths	10-2180 m
File format	SEG-Y
Listening time	10,000 ms
Sampling rate	0.5 ms
No. repeated shots	10
Far-offset check shot	After each large 50 m chain movement
No. of traces per shot	75

Figure 14. Processing flow for zero-offset VSP in K-18.

5.2.2 Raw data example

The raw, pre-processed shot gather (vertical component, VZ) is shown in Figure 15. Here, the traces are depth sorted and bad traces, i.e. traces with low SNR, are removed. As one can see, the data are of good overall quality, showing strong first downgoing P-wave arrival and clear first breaks, which are used to calculate seismic velocities along the well path. Although reflections, i.e. upgoing events, are difficult to identify, some crossing patterns can be seen.

Figure 15. K-18 raw zero-offset data example of the vertical component (VZ) after pre-processing. Horizontal axis in depth (m), vertical in time (0-4000 ms).

5.2.3 Processing results

As a result of the zero-offset processing, the upgoing wavefield is separated. It contains primary and multiple reflections from the subsurface along and below the well path. The corridor stacks for both P-wave and S-wave reflections are then generated. They can be used to identify primary reflections along and below the well path. In Section 7.1, they are also used to identify lithological horizons and compare them with other well log data. In terms of temporal resolution, the frequency bandwidth could be increased to about 5-80 Hz. Furthermore, seismic velocities are calculated for both P- and S-waves. The calculated velocities are shown in Figure 16, and the results of the processing are summarized in Figure 17.

Figure 16. Comparison of interval velocities and Vp/Vs ratios. Picked intervals based on key lithological boundaries.

Figure 17. K-18 processed VZ component of the zero-offset VSP. From left to right: Full stack of seismic section, outer corridor stack, vertical component of the NMO corrected P-wave VSP section. Upper right corner: Resulting amplitude spectrum after processing. Horizontal axis in depth (m), vertical axis in time (ms).

Table 6. Summary of the data deliverables for the VSP at well K-18 (cf. Appendix A.11).

#	Deliverable	File type
1	First break P-wave picks	XLS-Table
2	First break S-wave picks	XLS-Table
3	P-wave average and interval velocities	XLS-Table
4	S-wave average and interval velocities	XLS-Table
5	P-wave VSP NMO Section (final processed P-wave section)	SEG-Y
6	P-wave VSP full stack and corridor stacks (in TWT and depth)	SEG-Y
7	S-wave VSP NMO section (final processed S-wave section)	SEG-Y
8	S-wave VSP full stack and corridor stacks (in TWT and depth)	SEG-Y

5.3. ZO VSP processing | K-26

5.3.1 Processing flow

An overview of the processing flow is shown in Figure 18. The corresponding survey details are summarized in Table 7. The overall processing does not vary from that of well K-18. Nevertheless, the effective depth range is limited to only 1438 m (2170 m for K-18).

Table 7. K-26 zero-offset VSP summary.

No. of geophones	15 levels (lower-most 6 clamped)
Intertool distance	10 m
Reference point	10 m above first geophone
No. overlapped positions	1
Receiver station interval	2.5 m
Real measured depths	10-1448 m
File format	SEG-Y
Listening time	10 000 ms
Sampling rate	0.5 ms
No. repeated shots	10-20
Far-offset check shot	After each large 50 m chain movement
No. of traces per shot	69

Figure 18. Processing flow for zero-offset VSP in well K-26.

5.3.2 Raw data example

The raw, pre-processed zero-offset VSP data are shown in Figure 19. Here, all three-components of the data are displayed and sorted by increasing depth. In comparison to the zero-offset VSP from well K-18, the data have lower overall quality and SNR, due to much more noise caused by, e.g. the proximity to the power plant and the temperature conditions inside the well. As a result, additional trace editing was necessary to increase the data quality and SNR.

Figure 19. K-26 raw zero-offset 3C data. Left and middle: horizontal components, right: vertical component. Horizontal axis in depth (m), vertical axis in time (ms).

5.3.3 Processing results

As a result of the zero-offset VSP at well K-26 the upgoing wavefield and corridor stacks were determined for both P- and S-waves. Figure 20 shows the final processed, NMO corrected upgoing wavefield and corridor stacks. P- and S-wave velocity analyses were also carried out. The results are shown in Figure 21. Here, reflections along the well and also from below the borehole can be easily determined. Some dominant reflections can be seen below 1000 m and also at about 150 m.

Figure 20. K-26 processed VZ component of the zero-offset VSP. From left to right: Full stack of seismic section, outer corridor stack, vertical component of the NMO corrected P-wave section. Horizontal axis in depth (m), vertical axis in time (ms).

Figure 21. Results of velocity processing from well K-26. Left: interval velocities based on RTT plots (orange line) and a 30 m receiver interval (blue); right: Vp/Vs ratio based on RTT intervals.

Table 8. Summary of the data deliverables for the VSP at well K-26 (cf. Appendix A.11).

#	Deliverable	File type
9	First-break P-wave picks	XLS-Table
10	First break S-wave picks	XLS-Table
11	P-wave interval velocities	XLS-Table
12	S-wave interval velocities	XLS-Table
13	P-wave VSP NMO Section (final processed P-wave section)	SEG-Y
14	P-wave VSP full stack and corridor stacks (in TWT and depth)	SEG-Y
15	S-wave VSP NMO Section (final processed S-wave section)	SEG-Y
16	S-wave VSP full stack and corridor stacks (in TWT and depth)	SEG-Y

5.4 Source comparison

To assess the potential of different seismic sources in a volcanic environment, five different types of sources were tested during the VSP survey:

- DynaCORD line (source CORD in figure 12)
- Air gun (sources JON and INGI)
- Dynamite
 - in far-offset water pond (source THORSTEIN)
 - in 9 m cased drill shot holes (sources THOR1-THOR12)
 - in crater lake Víti (sources VITIA and VITIB)

The DynaCORD line source and the air gun source had approximately the same offset to the receiver well (see Figure 12). For the comparison, the amplitude spectra and SNR for one DynaCORD, air gun and dynamite shot are calculated and compared. The shots are also visually compared and shown in Figure 22. It can be shown that the air gun provided the stronger signal energies that are approximately 4-10 times stronger than that of the DynaCORD source.

In summary, the DynaCORD source shows relatively good image quality, and with signals 3-4 times stronger than average noise. Furthermore, the DynaCORD has a higher frequency content than all other sources. The different source spectra are shown in Figure 23.

Figure 22. Visual comparison of signal received in well K-18 from different types of sources (THORSTEIN, THOR12, CORD and INGI). Lowermost receivers (i.e. levels 12-17 or 10-15, respectively) are clamped. Vertical axis in time (ms).

Figure 23. Spectrum comparison of different sources. Raw amplitudes are displayed in [μV].

5.5 Further processing

5.5.1 Kästner MSc

As part of a Master's project (Appendix A.8) at the TU Bergakademie Freiberg and in collaboration with the Helmholtz Centre Potsdam GFZ, the zero- and far-offset VSP shots from well K-18 were processed. In the work, standard 1C and 3C processing, as well as imaging techniques were tested to assess their potential for mapping subsurface structures, not only in the vicinity, but also below and away from the well. Velocity analyses from P- and S-wave first arrivals are used to generate a first one-dimensional (1D) velocity model along the well path.

Figure 24. Overview of the processing flow used in the thesis (Kästner, Appendix A.8).

The processing flow (see Figure 24) comprises a pre-processing part and a processing part. The former includes trace sorting, trace editing and vertical stacking of the raw recorded data. The latter is further distinguished into a 1C zero-offset part used to create the reduced upgoing wavefield and the corridor stack to map reflections along the well path, and the 3C processing for both zero- and far-offset shot necessary for the proper 3D migration. The results of the 1C zero-offset processing are in good accordance with the processing results described in the previous sections,

showing some clear reflections along the well which can be tied to the transition between lava and hyaloclastite formations mapped from well cutting analyses. Furthermore, some stronger mode-converted downgoing and reflected waves could be seen.

Additionally, in this thesis, 3C seismic migration were carried out and tested. Seismic migration is used to map reflectors to their true subsurface positions and collapse diffractions. It can therefore be used to delineate detailed subsurface structures like fault planes (Yilmaz, 1987). Its first geometrical interpretation is treated by Hagedoorn (1954) and based on the analogy between diffraction curves (curves of maximum convexity) and the summation of isochrones. The illumination is thereby crucially dependent on the source-receiver coverage (aperture) as well as the survey geometry itself.

Two migration methods were applied: Kirchhoff depth migration (Schneider, 1978) and Fresnel volume migration (e.g., Lüth et al., 2005), which are based on the integral formulation of the wave equation. Both methods rely on the so-called diffraction stack integral which is evaluated for all source-receiver combinations and which describes a weighted summation of amplitudes along diffraction curves. The Fresnel volume migration is a modified Kirchhoff depth migration introducing an additional weighting factor based on the physically defined Fresnel zone and thus constraining the migration operator to the area that only constructively contributes to a reflection event. Especially, for surveys with a low spatial coverage of sources and receivers it helps to reduce migration artefacts resulting in a more focused image of the migrated events (Buske et al., 2009).

All three components are considered in the migration procedure in order to map reflections in all three dimensions in space. For the proper estimation of the emergent angle of the arriving waves at the receivers, those needed to be rotated previous to the migration process. A constant velocity model for P- and S-waves ($v_P=4.6$ km/s, $v_S=2.7$ km/s) is used. These are the mean velocities determined from the averaged interval velocities of the downgoing first arrivals. The image grid extends 3 km in x-direction, 1 km in y-direction, and 4 km in z-direction, where z represents the depth of the ground level at K-18. All four wave modes (PP, SS, SP and PS) are migrated separately and stacked in a final migrated image. Figure 25 shows one plane of the migrated image for PP and SS modes for the zero- and far-offset shots, respectively. The final stacked image can be found Chapter 7.2 (Figure 35). For a more detailed treatment of the applied migration procedure refer to the thesis attached to this report (Appendix A.8; Chapter 4.4).

Figure 25. 2D plane ($y=0$ m) of the single migrated zero-offset (ZO) and far-offset (FO) shot using Fresnel volume migration (FVM) with a constant velocity model. Shown are only results for P-wave (PP) and S-wave (SS) reflections. Star marks the source location (Kästner, Appendix A.8).

Results reveal reflections not only along, but also below the well trajectory for the zero-offset shot. Lateral reflections can hardly be determined because only upgoing waves were considered and the source offset (aperture) is too small in terms of the reflection angles. For the far-offset shot where the source is at a greater distance to the well some dipping reflections could be encountered also 500–1000 m away from the well. Furthermore, strong reflections below the well can be seen. These mainly result from the migrated S-wave modes which seem to suffer less from attenuation in the volcanic environment. It can also be an indication of the deeper rooted magma chamber between 2.5–3 km depth by assuming that it would result in stronger S-wave reflectivity. These results represent a highly simplified first attempt (like a constant velocity model and only two shot locations) but give an indication of the potential of the applied migration methods. It could be shown that it is possible to map or image seismic reflections where there is no or just little information about the subsurface geology of a geothermal reservoir. Further investigations are necessary to achieve a better focusing and lateral extent of the migrated image.

5.5.2 Microseismicity

The microseismic processing was performed by Volker Oye, NORSAR (Norway) for all monitoring data mostly recorded during nights in well K-18 and well K-26 (Appendix A.3). The processing was performed automatically with tuned and trained algorithms to identify local microseismic events in the proximity of the wells. In a first detection round, events were automatically detected by an STA/LTA detector and windowed grouping, requiring at least 10 geophones triggering a signal within a 400 ms time window. The settings were chosen to be conservative in order to avoid missing small events and rather include falsely triggered events in the further processing. The second step is a manual QC of these data, focusing on microseismic events from depth and rejecting falsely triggered events, which could be identified as noise sources from the surface and as noise sources from within the well (e.g. tube waves). Once microseismic events were positively identified a semi-automatic P- and S-wave picking was carried out. Finally, a full grid search on a 10 m grid for the event localization was performed, using pre-calculated P and S travel times within a 1D background velocity model obtained from the integrated interpretations of the sonic and VSP velocity data ($V_p/V_s = 1.8$).

A detailed description of the microseismic processing, conducted with NORSAR's in-house microseismic processing software, is found in Appendix A.3. Figure 26 shows an example of a microseismic event detected at well K-18. A large amount of the detected events results from surface noise and is often recognized as Stonely or tube waves. However, a total number of 53 microseismic events were detected and localized at well K-18 and these locations were confined between about 1 and 3 km depth. No microseismic events were detected at well K-26.

Figure 26. Example of a detected microseismic event on June 1st 2014 at 18:59:41. Blue bars show automatically picked and manually refined P-wave onsets and orange bars show S-wave onsets (Appendix A.3).

6 Borehole volcanology and wireline logs

As a part of Task 4.2 additional logging and borehole analysis was performed in the two Krafla wells used for the VSP study. Sonic velocity and televiwer logs were run in well K-18 along with additional borehole cuttings analysis whereas the high temperatures in K-26 precluded the running of these extra logs. Interpretation and integration of these new data are presented in a number of separate reports contained within the appendices of this report (e.g. Appendices A.4, A.5, A.6 and A.7). In the following sections, summaries of the updated interpretations from the analysis, compiled with the previous results from the wells, are presented.

6.1 K-18 borehole summary

A summary of the geological model for the K-18 borehole is presented in Figure 27. The borehole geological model has been updated based on additional analysis carried out as part of the IMAGE project including sonic log data, televiwer data and additional cuttings analysis. Due to casing down to 663 m, no sonic log data could be collected in this upper part. By characterizing the NN vs. sonic V_p relationship for the well below this depth, a relationship was tested and applied to the upper part of the well to give a pseudo-velocity log for the upper part of the well (Appendix A.6). This allows reasonable inference to the velocity structure of the upper part of the well and a basis for comparison with the VSP interval and average velocity data results.

The uppermost c. 380 m of well K-18 is composed of a mixed sequence of hyaloclastites, scoria, volcanoclastic units and sparse lavas conventionally referred to as "móberg" facies in Iceland. This sequence is underlain by a sequence of basaltic lavas, which progressively gives way to basaltic intrusions down to a depth of c. 800 m. A clear change from basalt intrusions to hyaloclastite at 800 m depth is evident in both cuttings and wireline data. The hyaloclastite formation, which is recorded at c. 800–1080 m depth, is composed of two main units based on wireline log character and cuttings evidence. The upper unit 4a (Figure 27) includes remnant pumice textures and a generally leucocratic pale color supporting the evidence (from high gamma values in the lower part) for more evolved tephra compositions. The lower unit 4b comprises increased amounts of basaltic cuttings mixed with the paler cuttings and a very clear change in log character, whereby thin high velocity units are interdigitated with the lower V_p background. This is interpreted to comprise a similar sequence to unit 4a but with the addition of interlayers of thin intrusions or possibly also thin lavas.

Beneath the hyaloclastite sequence, intrusion-dominated crystalline basalt predominates down to c. 1600 m. A thin c. 80 m thick interval of highly altered cuttings is identified from which primary textures are not decipherable. The unit is thought to comprise a layer of completely altered hyaloclastite or tuff but could also potentially represent a completely altered fracture zone where leaching has destroyed any original rock textures. Two prominent high gamma peaks below this unit may represent more evolved intrusions but associated low sonic velocities suggest either that they are highly altered or potentially that they could also originate from K-bearing secondary alteration products. Below this altered sequence from c. 1680 m, crystalline basalt and gabbroic intrusions are recorded uninterrupted down to the bottom of the well at c. 2200 m supported by high NN and sonic V_p values. A clear increase in V_p , NN and resistivity data at c. 1880 m is inferred to represent the transition from minor sheet intrusions into gabbroic basement.

Figure 27. Summary of the main logging units, borehole cuttings analysis and summary interpretation for borehole K-18.

6.2 K-26 borehole summary

No new log data were collected from the K-26 well aside from the VSP data largely due to the significantly higher temperature of the well compared to K-18. No new data, therefore, exists to update the current ÍSOR geological model (Figure 28). This interpretation is, therefore, used in the project. In order to give some inference to the borehole velocity structure of K-26, the K-18 derived NN vs. sonic velocity relationship was used to make a pseudo-velocity log for K-26 (Appendix A.6). The uppermost 770 m of K-26 consist of successions of extrusive rocks, which can be divided into two sequences of hyaloclastites separated by a pile of basalt lavas at 200–430 m depth. An intrusive complex is present below 770 m, consisting of a sheeted dyke complex, which extends down to almost 2 km, below which coarse grained dolerites and granophyre intrusions predominate. High NN values support the presence of dikes below approximately 800 m depth. Intrusions of more felsic compositions are inferred by the gamma ray logs as they result in high counts at ca. 970, 1670, 1960–1990, 2030–2040 and 2060–2110 m.

Figure 28. ÍSOR Petrel model stratigraphy and log data for K-26 plotted against the NN derived pseudo Vp log (see Appendix A.6 for details).

7 VSP integrated interpretation

7.1 K-18 borehole

The processed zero-offset VSP data for the K-18 well is compared and integrated with the borehole geological model and wireline data in this section. Within Appendix A.10, a full comparison of the lithological cuttings logs, wireline data and VSP data and analysis for K-18 are presented. First break arrival times (FB in ms) representing the P-wave and S-wave first arrivals are used along with offset-corrected source to receiver distances (D) provided by DECO (Appendix A.2).

Figure 29 displays a plot of reduced travel time (RTT) for the VSP Vp first breaks along with summary information on the borehole geology. Reduced travel times were calculated as $FB-D/4$ for Vp data. RTT is used to display the difference in velocity for the well using a reduction velocity of 4 km/s. Intervals with velocities slower than this values will cause RTT to increase, whereas intervals with velocities faster than this value will cause RTT to decrease. RTT versus depth plots reveal the following inferences:

1. Constant values with depth: interval with divisor velocity
2. Linear gradient increasing with depth: unit slower than divisor velocity
3. Linear gradient decreasing with depth: unit faster than divisor velocity
4. Curved gradients: increasing or reducing velocity within unit
5. Inflections, scatter or short wavelength variance: strong impedance boundaries, local heterogeneity and dipping units such as dykes or fractures

Table 9. Summary of the reduced travel time RTT VSP Vp interval velocities for K-18 borehole. Sonic velocities for L1-L4 estimated as outlined in Appendix A.6 and are therefore borehole based estimates and not velocity measurements (colored orange). * Vp derived from neutron log data (NN), ++ Vp estimated from borehole cuttings inference (high uncertainty).

VSP RTT Vp		Downhole depth		VSP			Log	VSP / log comparison	
Interval	Slope	Top (m)	Bottom (m)	Vp (km/s)	Vs (km/s)	Vp/Vs	Vp _L (km/s)	Vp-Vp _L (km/s)	Vp-Vp _L (%)
L1	+	30	200	3.04	1.44	2.11	3.36++	-0.32	-10.66
L2	+	200	372	3.59	2.03	1.77	3.31*	0.28	7.86
L3	=	372	552	3.96	2.18	1.81	4.54*	-0.58	-14.78
L4	-	552	790	4.52	2.50	1.81	4.96*	-0.44	-9.65
L5	+	790	930	3.54	2.37	1.49	2.70	0.84	23.70
L6	=	930	1120	4.13	2.58	1.60	3.13	1.00	24.21
L7	-	1120	1585	5.04	3.05	1.65	4.56	0.47	9.42
L8	-	1585	1662	4.95	2.82	1.76	4.33	0.62	12.55
L9	-	1662	1800	4.52	2.96	1.53	4.54	-0.02	-0.44
L10	-	1800	2200	6.07	3.62	1.68	5.45	0.62	10.17
Logged interval	n/a	660	2165	4.82	2.93	1.65	4.43	0.39	8.18

Figure 29. VSP Vp Reduced Travel Time (RTT) and borehole sonic log (green solid line) plotted against depth for the K-18 well. The pseudo-sonic data are indicated by a dashed green line (Appendices A.4 and A.6). Intervals with similar average velocities are interpreted based on the RTT versus depth gradient and labelled L1-L10. Pink = avg. velocity < 4 km/s, orange = avg. velocity ~4 km/s, blue = avg. velocity > 4 km/s. Arrows display the main gradient breaks. Borehole logging and lithological units, defined in Appendix A.4, are displayed on the left (gray boxes) and on the right respectively.

In K-18 the RTT displays a number of clear transitions between units with largely linear average velocity trends along with a number of narrow intervals of inflection and scattering points. Based on these variations in Vp RTT, ten broad VSP intervals (L1 to L10) have been defined for well K-18 (Figure 29). These intervals are interpreted to correspond to lithological successions with relatively consistent average velocities (Table 9). The transitions between these units vary from strong gradient changes, as for example between L1 to L2 and L6 to L7, to less pronounced changes as for L5 to L6. Unit L8 comprises a short heterogeneous interval with a rapid +/- shift away from the background decreasing gradient.

Using the intervals defined from the VSP RTT, averaged interval velocities are calculated for Vp, Vs along with the Vp/Vs ratios and compared to the sonic log and pseudo sonic interval velocities (Table 9) in Figure 30. The sonic Vp is between c. 0 to 1 km/s slower than the VSP derived interval velocities. The velocity difference is possibly due to the increased borehole condition dependency of the sonic log data or dikes acting as high-velocity VSP wave-guides as suggested by synthetic modelling (Figure 9). The compiled derived velocity (from NN and cuttings inference, Appendix A.6) also shows a close fit to the VSP data +/- c. 0.6 km/s.

RTT from VSP S-wave data has also been generated using a reduction velocity of 2.35 km/s (FB-D/2.35) for comparison to the Vp RTT results (Figure 30). There is in general good correspondence between the Vp and Vs RTT. A notable inflection is observed at c. 1400 m within unit L7 Vs RTT data which is less well constrained in the Vp RTT. Other than this, the broad boundary transitions appear relatively well linked between Vp and Vs.

It is clear that most of the main unit transitions derived from the VSP RTT analysis correspond very closely to the major wireline log unit boundaries interpreted for the K-18 well. These logging units correspond to major lithological boundaries based on the integrated geological model for K-18 (Appendix A.4; see figure 29). However, not all of the unit boundaries from the VSP RTT analysis correspond to clear boundaries from the geological model as for instance the lower boundary of L5 and L9 both occur c. 80 m and c. 30 m above the nearest major boundaries in the geological model. In the case of L9 lower boundary, the RTT character change between the units is clear but there is also a lower velocity unit just above this transition (Figure 30). The basement transition in K-18 is due to a high velocity dense gabbroic body which at one point will have comprised a large magma chamber. It is common in intrusion scenarios for tongues of magma to invade into the roof rock (e.g. Figure 31) and therefore it is entirely possible that the very high sonic log response at c. 1760 m could be such a feature as it displays velocities equal to the basement gabbro. Intruded scenarios with irregular geometries and connectivity outside the borehole path could have caused significant scattering or focusing effects on the VSP derived waves.

Figure 30. Comparison of VSP Vs and Vp Reduced Travel Time (RTT) with borehole sonic data for the K-18 well and interval velocities including Vp, Vs, Vp/Vs and borehole sonic. Reduction velocities are 4 and 2.35 km/s, respectively for Vp and Vs RTT.

Figure 31. Field example of large basaltic sills connected by small intrusions. The two large sills are connected by smaller apophyses and feeder dykes which breached the roof rock of the initial large intrusion (Ferrari LIP, South Victoria Land; Muirhead et al., 2014).

The seismograms derived from the VSP, V_p and V_s data corridor stacks are compared to the wireline logs and the geological borehole data in Figure 32. An initial integration of the main reflectivity has been carried out with a focus on:

1. VSP facies: broad intervals with similar amplitude and frequency characteristics
2. Major transitions between intervals with different reflectivity characteristics
3. Isolated reflections

By comparing the geological model, wireline data and relative amplitudes of the VSP corridor stacks, reflections have been identified and rated in terms of relative prominence in Figure 32. Of key importance is the strong correspondence of the broad VSP facies with the borehole geological model. In a number of cases clear geological boundaries appear relatively diffuse or protracted from the VSP reflectivity. In these cases, as discussed above, the boundaries may either be dipping or be very rough or heterogeneous which will promote scattering and ringing.

To demonstrate the wide-ranging characteristics observed within the VSP V_p reflectivity, V_p corridor stacks and traces are shown at the same vertical resolution and superimposed next to each other in Figure 33. The wide variation in character is clear. Given the association of these key VSP facies with the well-constrained borehole geological model it is possible to interpret seismic facies changes related to the geological facies (Figure 33).

The water level in the K-18 borehole is recorded as generally staying around c. 250 m below the surface however, fluctuations to levels as deep as c. 350 m were recorded prior to the VSP experiment. Water saturation has a first order effect on subsurface rock velocities and therefore the transition from saturated to unsaturated conditions at the water table should give a significant response within the K-18 VSP data. Evidence for relatively porous hyaloclastites, vesicular basalt and scoria in the upper c. 400 m of the well also support the likelihood that the saturation level will give a prominent signature within the VSP data.

Figure 32. Reflectivity analysis for K-18 VSP data based on VSP corridor stack (Appendix A.2), shown in right most panel and superimposed behind logs to aid comparison. Intervals with similar reflectivity are denoted as broadly similar VSP facies by different colored boxes, blue text describes the broad reflectivity facies. Key reflectivity transitions and events are annotated with possible causes based on the integrated borehole analysis. Borehole cuttings percentage logs are shown to the left followed by borehole logging units and sonic log.

VSP facies	Character	Volcanic facies
	High frequency High amplitude c. 320-520 m	Basalt lava dominated sequence <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong vertical heterogeneity • Repeated layering of fast lava cores with slower altered flow tops • Vp range commonly 2-5 km/s
	Low frequency High amplitude c. 600-800 m	Dolerite sheet intrusions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High average velocities • Sharp impedance contrasts at intrusion host rock boundaries • Thick intrusions or sub-vertical sheets may form wave guides
	Moderate frequency Very low amplitude c. 880-1180 m	Altered hyaloclastite / tuff <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dominated by fragmental highly altered material • Very low internal reflectivity unless intruded or including flow lobes • Slow restricted velocity histogram from log data
	Moderate frequency Very low amplitude c. 1480-1680 m	Dolerite sheet intrusions (deep) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High average velocities • Lack of impedance contrasts may represent higher percentage of intrusion to host with depth • Attenuation of down going energy by overlying volcanic pile
	Low frequency Moderate amplitude c. 1840-2140 m	Gabbroic basement <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very high velocity • High amplitude contact reflector • Relatively homogenous • Major impedance contrast at contact • Fracturing and mineral layering may provide heterogeneities

Figure 33. Examples of isolated VSP facies intervals from K-18 corridor stack including inference relating to the associated borehole volcanic facies.

By far the most obvious candidate for the water table in K-18 is at c. 200 m at the transition from VSP units L1 to L2, which is shallower than expected. This transition does not correspond to any significant transitions in the borehole geology model (based on cuttings) which appears also to support a fluid saturation origin for this unit transition. One possibility for the shallower than expected water table depth recorded by the VSP could be the casing of the upper part of K-18. Where variable hydrostatic heads within the lower sequence create an average hydrostatic head lower than that of the upper groundwater aquifers which are vertically isolated from the deeper zones by the casing e.g. Figure 34.

Figure 34. Schematic demonstration of the effects of aquifer isolation and drilling connectivity in layered basaltic sequences from the Columbia River Basalt Province modified after Burns et al. (2008). In context of the K-18 scenario, if borehole 5 was then cased and cemented across Aquifer 1, in time, recharge would re-equilibrate the potentiometric surface back to a higher level than the borehole in continued connection to Aquifer 2 creating a discrepancy between the hydrostatic head within and without the cased well section.

In summary, the VSP velocity data shows a generally strong correspondence with the major lithological intervals and boundaries recorded from well data in K-18. This analysis demonstrates that the VSP data can effectively image major lithological boundaries within heterogeneous, high scattering basaltic sequences. The evidence from the VSP RTT analysis implies that lithology has a primary control on the VSP velocity data in K-18. Four main water feed points are known from K-18 (Figure 32). These zones occur within a water saturated sub-surface sequence and, therefore, only relative volume coupled with host rock reservoir structure are likely to exhibit features which could be imaged by the VSP data given the relatively low temperatures of the K-18 well and the lack of a steam cap.

Of the four feed zones, none display obvious signatures within the RTT data. The feed zone at c. 900 m within the "moberg" formation corresponds closely to the inflection at the transition between VSP units L5 and L6 which does not correspond clearly to a lithological boundary and therefore the feed zone could impart an effect on the VSP data (Figure 27 and 29). However, no unique signature can be associated to a fluid response from the current data. The feed zone at c. 1680 m also corresponds closely to the base of a highly altered interval which has a strong RTT response. In this case the lithological variation appears to be the controlling factor on the VSP response as it begins c. 80 m above the feed zone but there is nevertheless a correspondence. The other two feed zones show no clear correspondence with the VSP data.

7.2 K-18 borehole look-ahead

VSP data can be used to map reflections in the vicinity of the well but also below the well ahead of the deepest geophone position. Reflections from deeper structures are arriving first at deepest geophone positions are less affected by near-surface attenuation and scattering.

In contrast to reflections determined along the well, which can be tied directly to well log data or geology, the interpretation of look-ahead data is less reliable. Depths from where reflections emerge cannot be determined reliably because velocities below the TD of the well are unknown.

Furthermore, it is more difficult to discriminate between primary reflections and reflections from e.g. inter-bed multiples.

Figure 35 shows some major P-wave reflections ahead of the well in the zero-offset shot. These events result from below the well and indicate impedance contrasts in the deeper subsurface. Reflections are relatively strong and suggest impedance boundaries around 1.5 s and below 2 s. It is most likely that these events are resulting from changes in lithology. Also some deeper S-wave reflections are visible (Figure 36). These events may be interpreted as the presence of magma which would result in a strong S-wave reflectivity. Other fluids or steam are not to be expected because they were not detected within the well and hence are more unlikely below the well. These observations show that it is possible to detect signals below 2 km depth with a single zero-offset air gun.

Figure 35. Results showing stacks and NMO corrected P-wave section of zero-offset VSP at well K-18. Here, the interpretation of reflections along the well trajectory and the look-ahead is highlighted. Some major reflections are marked by arrows for near well reflections (blue) and reflections below the deepest geophone position (below TD, green). Note that multiples and primaries cannot distinguished below TD.

Figure 36. Results showing stacks and NMO corrected S-wave section of zero-offset VSP at well K-18. Reflections along the well trajectory and the look-ahead are highlighted. Major reflections are marked by arrows for near well reflections (blue) and reflections below the deepest geophone position (below TD, green).

With help of the method of seismic migration, reflections are mapped to their true subsurface position. Here, a constant velocity model is assumed for the depth allocation of the reflections. This is only a first approximation but gives a first indication of the direction and the location of impedance contrasts and, hence, of reflections below TD. Figure 37 shows the final results from the Fresnel volume migration of the zero- and far-offset VSP recorded in K-18. Dominant reflections could be mapped in three-dimension for both shot locations and are marked by arrows (cf. letters Figure 37).

Amplitudes in the migrated sections are spread strongly along semi-circles (or spheroids in 3D). This is because of the sparse source-receiver coverage. These migration artefacts can be mitigated by applying the Fresnel criteria to the migration procedure resulting in the better focusing of the migrated events.

From the zero-offset shot the strongest reflection amplitudes can be observed along the well path and above 1000 m depth. Below, amplitudes decrease with depth. This transition is associated with a major geological boundary which is also marked by a strong reflection both in the migrated and the processed sections. Further reflections can be seen around 750-800 m depth indicating the change of hyaloclastites to an intrusion dominated basaltic lava formation. Here, a major inflow zone is documented, too.

Figure 37. Results of depth migrated zero-offset (right) and far-offset VSP (left) at well K-18 using Fresnel volume migration with a constant velocity model ($V_p=4.6$ km/s; $V_p=2.7$ km/s). Some of the dominant reflections are marked by arrows and Latin letters (A-F). Sources are marked with a red star; the well with the placed receivers is marked in blue (Kästner, Appendix A.8).

Several smaller reflections in the uppermost 500 m indicate further transitions between the hyaloclastite and lava formations. The actual depth, however, can be better identified in the upgoing wave field and the corridor stack. Another strong reflection can be identified at 1.7 km depth and coincide with the top of the basement. Below the well, two main reflections at 2.5 km and 3 km depth can be seen for both the zero- and far-offset. The amplitudes for these reflectors mainly result from the SS migrated wave modes indicating a strong S-wave reflectivity. One explanation can be the presence of a magmatic body or intrusion.

7.3 K-26 borehole

In this section the processed zero-offset VSP data is used for an integration with the borehole geological model and the associated well logs. Because of severe well conditions (active injector) as well as lower S/R ratios an integrated interpretation is more difficult than for well K-18. Furthermore, the VSP data is constrained to a measured depth of 1448 m, whereas the total depth of the well is 2115 m. Nevertheless, P- and S-wave picks could be used to calculate RTT plots as well as interval velocities which could be used for a direct comparison with the wireline data and lithological succession derived from cutting analyses. Stacks from NMO corrected VSP data converted to depths are used to assess the sensitivity of the seismic wave field to well-known boundaries along the well. The VSP data, including stacks, first break times and velocities, are provided by DECO (Appendix A.2).

Figure 38 displays reduced travel time plots for processed P and S wave VSP data alongside the derived pseudo-sonic velocity log and ÍSOR geological model for well K-25. Similar to the K-18 section described above, key boundaries and intervals with similar velocities have been picked based on the more reliable P-wave velocity picks. The most prominent change within the sampled interval is at the base of RTT interval L6 where a sharp change from dominantly < 4 km/s average velocities to higher velocities >4 km/s occurs. This change corresponds precisely with the geological change from mixed Hraun (lava) and Móberg (hyalastite) formations into a dominantly intruded section. This gives strong evidence that the VSP data is capable of picking out major lithology boundaries within the sub-surface, even in the challenging high temperature conditions of wells such as K-26. A wider variation is observed within the S-wave RTT data which may provide further insight into fluids of varying temperature in future studies. Table 10 summarizes the interval average data presented in Figure 38.

Figure 38. VSP Vp and Vs Reduced Travel Time (RTT) and Vp/Vs versus depth plotted against NN derived pseudo-sonic log data (discussed in Appendix 6) for the K-26 well. Intervals with similar average velocities are interpreted based on the RTT versus depth gradient and labelled L1-L9. Pink = avg. velocity < 4 km/s, orange = avg. velocity ~4 km/s, blue = avg. velocity > 4 km/s. Arrows display the main gradient breaks. Reduction velocities are 4 and 2.35 km/s respectively for Vp and Vs.

Table 10. Summary of the interval velocities within well K-26. Intervals were picked based on changes in RTT gradient and inflections from the P-wave data.

VSP RTT Vp		Downhole depth		VSP		
Interval	Slope	Top (m)	Bottom (m)	Vp (km/s)	Vs (km/s)	Vp/Vs
L1	+	102.5	197.6	2.44	1.81	1.34
L2	+	197.6	282.4	3.36	2.00	1.68
L3	-	282.4	352.4	4.46	1.84	2.42
L4	+	352.4	450.0	3.35	1.77	1.89
L5	+	450.0	655.0	3.57	2.03	1.76
L6	=	655.0	737.6	4.08	2.54	1.60
L7	-	737.6	987.5	5.97	3.14	1.90
L8	-	987.5	1376.0	5.12	3.04	1.68
L9	=	1376.0	1454.0	3.99	4.25	0.94
Logged interval	n/a	102.5	1456	4.17	2.47	1.69

7.4 K-26 borehole look-ahead

At well K-26 the deepest measured depth was at about 1450 m (last geophone at 1448 m depth). The total vertical depth of the well is 2115 m. Hence, near well reflections are only reliable for the uppermost two-thirds. Reflections from deeper locations must be handled with care as described in the previous section. Although, it provides the possibility to assess the potential of a zero-offset look-ahead at least for the lowermost 665 m where well logs are still available and which can be tied to reflections detected below TD.

As shown in Figure 39, reflections can be detected along the well and also below TD (total depth). Here, some stronger events are visible, e.g. at about 0.8, 1.5 and 2.2 s TWT (two-way-time), and can mainly be addressed to reflectors in the gabbro/dolerite dominated basement. No strong reflections are detectable within the lowermost parts of the well below TD and the total vertical depth (2115 m). A first stronger reflection below TD appears at about 800 ms TWT. It lies in the deepest parts of the well and could be caused by intrusions. Another strong reflection appears at about 1.5 s both for the P- and the S-waves. For an estimate velocity of 4 km/s this reflection may emerge from depths around 3.5 km and may indicate the presence of magma or an active intrusion.

Figure 39. Results showing stacks and NMO corrected section of zero-offset VSP at well K-26. Here, the interpretation of reflections along the well trajectory and the look-ahead is highlighted. Some major reflections are marked by arrows for near well reflections (blue) and reflections below the last geophone position (below TD, green). Note that multiples and primaries cannot be distinguished below TD. Two-way-time (TWT) is in ms and depth in m.

8 Microseismicity interpretation

As a result of the microseismic data processing (see Appendix A.3) a total number of 53 microseismic events are detected, identified and located in the proximity of well K-18. With respect to the limited amount of available data due to short recording times, this represents a relatively large amount of microseismicity that could be located. Moreover, the monitoring is purely passive, no active water injection or stimulation was taking place during the monitoring periods. Keeping this in mind, there is a large potential for microseismic monitoring and its interpretation. Microseismic monitoring was conducted at selected depths between 400 and 2010 m below the surface, however, microseismicity could only be detected at deployment depths of 1557, 1630 and 2010 m with relatively high detection rates. At depths of 400 to 500 m as well as in K-26, no microseismic events could be detected. The latter can be explained by the high noise levels from fluid injection even sensed at greater depth (1750 m) and where VSP data also provide low data quality or no data at all.

We have shown that microseismic monitoring is a viable tool for the detection of active fracture zones, even with very small magnitude microseismic activity. Furthermore, the location of microseismic events in volcanic regions seems to be useful for the identification of the brittle-ductile boundary. In this study, even though the observation times are too short to make a firm interpretation, no seismicity occurred deeper than 3000 m depth and a clear clustering of microseismic activity was between 2000 and 2500 m depth. This could be indicative of a rim of a magma chamber. Several microseismic events could be identified very close to the previously drilled magmatic pockets-s (well K-39), about 300 m lateral distance to K-18 at depths from 2000 to 2500 m depth (cf. Figure 40).

Currently, none of the located microseismic events could be identified on any of the permanent or semi-permanent seismic surface stations, neither were there any events detected with recording depths at 400-500 m depth. This can be an indication for the small magnitude of the events and/or relatively high attenuation, potentially by scattering in the uppermost parts of the volcanic rocks.

In essence, microseismic monitoring can be applied as an exploration tool for geothermal energy and should be continued for the purpose of identification of active fault zones and mapping of brittle-ductile transition zones, also applying tomographic methods and advanced microseismic analysis interpretation. Hereby, an enhanced sensor layout, especially at greater depths may be advantageous. Further recommendations, especially concerning the Krafla experiments can be found the microseismicity report in Appendix A.3.

Figure 40. Schematic picture with cross section around well K-18. Several hours of passive seismic data have provided microseismic locations. All of them are shallower than 3000 m depth, and there is a clustering between 2000 and 2500 m depth, potentially aligned with fault zones. Longer observation times are required to make these first findings more reliable (Oye, Appendix A.3).

9 Conclusions

The main objective of Task 4.2 was to assess the applicability of VSP surveying as a method for sub-surface mapping in volcanic geothermal fields to determine 1) volcanic stratigraphy and stratigraphic boundaries, 2) fractures and dikes and 3) fluids (water, gas, magma). A secondary objective was to test the complementary use of microearthquakes and noise recorded by surface network and well bore recordings. The focus of Task 4.2 was to acquire data in one well, K-18, in the Krafla high-temperature field in NE-Iceland. However, a lot of additional data were acquired including a zero-offset VSP in well K-26, a limited multi-offset VSP, and passive seismic data.

The operations were done in May/June 2014 using a VSP receiver string consisting of 17 three-component geophones. The six lowermost geophones were clamped. The receiver interval was 2.5 m for the zero-offset VSP. In addition, data were recorded on 14 permanent seismic stations, 23 temporary Reftec stations, and 48 planted geophones. Air gun (10 shots at each depth level), DynaCORD, and dynamite shots in shallow boreholes and ponds were used as sources. In total, 2861 air gun, 145 dynamite and 1 DynaCORD shots were recorded. New borehole data in borehole K-18 included acquisition of sonic and televiewer wireline log data and geological re-interpretation of cuttings data.

The operations were successful. Initial QC processing showed that good VSP data could be obtained from both air gun and dynamite sources. Source comparison further revealed that air gun and dynamite (borehole, pond, and DynaCORD) shots gave good to reasonable signal-to-noise ratios in the more than 2 km deep boreholes. Clamped receivers, however, had a much better signal-to-noise ratio than the noisy unclamped receivers. This was observed for the active VSP acquisition and also during passive seismic monitoring for microearthquakes.

Operationally, high-temperature geothermal fields are challenging. Cooling of the boreholes was required to lower the formation temperature. Geophones with a higher-temperature rating would be useful for future surveys.

The average sonic velocity in the uncased interval of K-18 (660-2165 m) is 4.43 km/s, whereas the velocity of the first P-wave arrival from the VSP is 8.2 % higher (4.82 km/s). Interval velocities in layers interpreted from reduced travel time plots give up to 24% higher velocities from the VSP data. The higher velocities of the VSP data could be due to steeply dipping high-velocity dikes. Alternatively fracturing in the vicinity of the borehole could lower the sonic log velocity more than the velocity derived from the low-frequency VSP data. The televiewer data were generally of low quality (Appendices A.5 and A.6). The log quality could likely be improved by adjusting the tool setting and logging speed (Appendix A.6). Improved imaging logs could be useful for identifying fractures and steeply dipping dikes, which could help to determine the cause of the observed velocity differences. Improved structural information would also be useful to generate velocity models for synthetic modelling and survey planning.

Comparison between depth-converted zero-offset VSP stacked data and borehole log and geological data reveal distinct correlation between VSP seismic facies and reflections and the downhole geology. In K-18 the uppermost 800 m has high-amplitude P-wave reflections in a basalt and intruded sequence, whereas the hyaloclastite and dolerite interval from 800 to 1680 m is characterized by low amplitude reflections. The gabbroic basement down to TD of 2140 is characterized by intermediate amplitudes and a high-amplitude reflection near the top of the basement. Several seismic reflections are furthermore identified ahead of the borehole both in the zero-offset and the multiple-offset VSP data. There are several distinct S-wave reflections both in and ahead of the borehole. A P-wave event at ca. 1.5 s (~3.5 km) depth may indicate the presence of magma. High-amplitude S-wave reflections may possibly be interpreted as originating from an intrusion as magma has lower S-wave velocities than solid rocks. There are no major fluid injection zones or steam caps in K-18, thus the imaging of such zones could not be accomplished by the zero-offset VSP.

In total, 53 microseismic events have been detected during the short monitoring periods within K-18. Microseismic events could only be detected when the geophones were lowered down to about 1500 m depth. This is due to the small size of the microseismic events, and improved signal to noise levels at depth (i.e. stronger signals due to closer proximity to the events, lower noise levels at larger deployment depth and less attenuation of the signal energy at depth as compared to shallower layers). Most detected and located events are clustered between 2000 and 2500 m, speculatively interpreted as faults that are located near the rim of a magma body. The location of the microseismic events may also be useful for detecting the brittle-ductile transition, estimated to be deeper than about 3000 m. During the short recording times downhole, no events were detected on the surface stations, documenting the importance of borehole receivers for microseismic studies.

Seismic imaging of heterogeneous igneous sequences is difficult. However, this study has shown that VSP experiments have a clear potential for imaging igneous complexes in geothermal areas. This includes:

- Upgoing P- and S-reflections can be recorded within the drilled sequence and from below the borehole.
- Zero-offset VSP data can be used to obtain velocity-depth functions, V_p/V_s ratios, and one-dimensional stacks.
- Multi-offset VSP can be used to image dipping and sub-well targets away from and below the borehole.

10 Outlook and integration

This project has shown that VSP experiments can be useful for imaging geothermal reservoirs. However, the method needs refinements to be cost-efficient. The imaging objectives should be well-defined, and seismic modelling prior to an experiment may benefit the survey planning and operations.

Typical survey objectives:

- Reservoir structure. Determination of dip and extent of a fractured layer away from the borehole (useful to optimize next borehole location and to understand reservoir properties).
- Mapping top of magma (geohazard and heat source applications).
- Mapping of the top of gas cap (reservoir management).

It is further important to assess if targets are mappable:

- Use seismic modeling studies to design the experiment.
- Assess the detectability and resolution of targets.
- Address the usefulness of revised regional velocity, attenuation, and reflectivity structure.
- Importance of S-wave imaging for fluid detection and possibly less attenuation.

10.1 Zero-offset VSP

Zero-offset VSP's can be done routinely and cost-efficiently by e.g. ÍSOR in combination with logging using:

- High-temperature clamped 3C receiver (or a short receiver string).
- Air gun and excavator for air-gun pit.
- Standard recording systems.
- Near real-time processing (send data to office or bring processing expert).
- No orientation shots.

For a time requirement of 1-2 minutes per shot (vertical fold of 10) and 2 minutes move time, about 20 shots can be acquired per hour. For a single receiver with recording interval of 2.5 m it will take about 20 hours to acquire VSP data for a 1 km sequence. Such a project, including processing, may be completed in less than a week. The results would be a P- and S-wave velocity profile, and corridor stacks of the well and ahead of the well. It would be preferential to have sonic velocity and imaging logs with structural interpretation prior to such a survey.

10.2 Multi-offset VSP

Multi-offset VSP are more extensive surveys that can be done during field development. It can be used for mapping dipping structures for e.g. well planning and to map geology in front of the borehole.

- Mapping of reservoir structure, including dipping fracture zones, for better reservoir development and management.
- Geohazard assessment, including mapping of magma and steam.

Possible work flow:

- Perform zero-offset experiment (source test, velocity structure, reflectivity structure, logging).
- Do survey design study of how to image and optimally illuminate key targets (fractures, reservoirs, magma).
- Determine source (air gun, dynacord, dynamite in ponds or boreholes, vibroseis).
- Determine downhole receiver string (high-temperature 3C receivers; 5-20 receivers).
- Evaluate need for surface receivers.
- Advanced processing and interpretation – need to refine current work flow.

10.3 Microseismic monitoring

Microseismic monitoring may be continued for the purpose of identification of active fault zones and mapping of brittle-ductile transition zones.

- Receiver deployment in deep wells is important. Due to high temperatures, this might be a challenge, but the deeper the sensors is, the more likely it is identify the small microseismic events.
- Install receivers in more than one vertical well, and conduct proper orientation and coupling of all sensors (see Figure 30).
- In open-hole wells, gasses and pressure pulses are often observed that might provide difficulties for passive seismic monitoring. Cementation of sensors is one way to come across this problem, casing and plugging the well properly is another. It is important to approach the potential issue of tube waves seriously.
- Number of sensors and spacing of these within a vertical well needs to be adjusted for monitoring purpose, and adequately modelled beforehand.
- Advanced processing methods can be applied for permanent installations, where seismicity occurs over long time. Repeating or similar microearthquakes can also be identified from noisy data, located with high accuracy relative to each other's locations, and detection thresholds will be lowered to smaller magnitude events using e.g. waveform cross-correlation methods.

10.4 Integration with other IMAGE work packages

The processing and interpretation of the main VSP data from K-18 are presented in this report. However, there is a lot of potential for further analyses of these data and some of the additional surface data that were acquired as a part of the field operations. Such future add-on projects could be useful to improved interpretation and work flows for planning, acquisition, processing and interpretation of VSP data in igneous geothermal reservoirs.

In Task 7.1 and Task 8.2 new processing techniques are developed and tested on site with focus on imaging geothermal properties within a basement/sedimentary environment. As a part of this work package Fabienne Reiser, Cedric Schmelzbach and Stewart Greenhalgh from ETHZ in Switzerland are focusing on the migration (imaging) of acoustic synthetic VSP data using the geological background information from Soultz-sous-Forêts and simulating different fracture zone dips and distances from the borehole. They use 2D and 3D geometries to investigate which fracture zone dips can be imaged using an optimal survey layout. Apart from a feasibility study, their focus lies on optimizing the survey design of a VSP experiment. From modelling analyses of P- and S-wave components it was observed that reflected energy at fractures mostly corresponds to P-S wave conversions. As a result they emphasize the importance of mode-converted waves and multicomponent seismic migration for shear wave birefringence analyses (Reiser, Greenhalgh and Schmelzbach, IMAGE Newsletter No.02, April 2015). Their insights from modelling studies will be used to improve the migration process of VSP data and will also be tested with this VSP data incorporating both zero- and far-offset data (MSP and far-offset dynamite shots) in the whole imaging process.

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12 List of appendices and data

- A.1 Field report (ÍSOR/GFZ/VBPR)
- A.2 Processing report (DECO)
- A.3 Microseismicity report (NORSAR)
- A.4 Borehole geology report (VBPR)
- A.5 Televiewer report (ÍSOR)
- A.6 Televiewer review (ÍSOR/VBPR)
- A.7 K-18 Sonic log report (ÍSOR)
- A.8 Thesis (GFZ/Kästner)
- A.9 Abstracts (GFZ/Kästner)
- A.10 K-18 Composite Panel (VBPR)
- A.11 List of project data

- Field data (ZO VSP, MSP, Geophone, Reftec, Seismometer, Navigation)
- Processed data (ZO VSP, NMO, corridor stack for P and S waves; velocity-depth curves/velocity models)
- Wireline log data

A.12 PowerPoint presentations (VBPR/DECO)

- vbpr-krafla14-FieldQC-v04.ppt
- Source_Comparison-v02.ppt

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